

TWO ESSAYS ON N. T. WRIGHT, 4 ESDRAS AND ORIGINAL SIN

Wright and wrong

Posted on 25/07/2013 by Jon Garvey

Penman, always helpful in providing useful links, has pointed me to a quotation from an interview with theologian N T Wright. In the wide-ranging interview by Andrew Wilson, he is asked about belief in a historical Adam and Eve.

After discussing the alternative extremes – treating Genesis 2-4 as literalistic history or dismissing it as theological fiction – he gives the bare bones of his own understanding:

So I then want to say that, in so far as I understand contemporary evolutionary biology, which is not my field at all, I am not a scientist, I think I want to say that yes, over millennia God created creatures we call hominids, but that at a specific time, just like God called Abraham and Sarah from among the other potentially nomadic peoples of the middle east and said *'you're going to be the bearers of my purpose'*, so God called an original primal pair and said *'Now this thing is fairly chaotic at the moment. You are going to be the ones through whom I am going to plant a garden and we're going to bring my wisdom, my stewardship, and my love into the world in a whole new way.'* And it seems to me that is a story one can tell with integrity, both as a serious reader of scripture and as somebody prepared to do business with contemporary science.

Wright introduces his remarks by saying it's not something he has given prolonged study to, but he does also remind us that he's spent time in discussions with *BioLogos* and so is not completely apart from the debate either.

A couple of things are interesting about this. The first is that one can get the impression that only Fundamentalist ostriches give any serious consideration to a historical Adam nowadays. In a particularly ill-tempered (and soon deleted) exchange on *BioLogos* a couple of years ago, Denis Lamoreux replied thus to Darrel Falk's stated policy of exploring the views of theologians who saw a first couple as historic, but not necessarily the sole genetic progenitors of humankind, though they are a minority:

Why do you think this is the case? It's because those of us who are trained in Old Testament realize that your view is utterly misguided. It's not what the Word of God says. But you and others like Denis Alexander are recalcitrant and refuse to listen. You're both like young earth creationists who refuse to listen when you speak on your academic specialty genetics.

Tom Wright, of course, is noted as a New Testament scholar, so perhaps Lamoreux would include him amongst those without the training necessary to comment on the issue. It's a shame if the demarcation disputes once seen in labour relations now only apply to biblical studies. But I venture to suggest that Wright has a broader view of Scripture than that – and

also note that Lamoreux's ally Peter Enns, though an OT scholar, is not averse to telling us "how it is" regarding the NT.

More intrinsically helpful, though, is some of Wright's incisive reasoning for his position – for which he *does* draw on the New Testament:

[T]he first thing to say is that it is very interesting that in the Old Testament itself hardly anything is made of Adam, which is kind of curious to a Christian looking at it. So when I started to work on Romans I assumed that an Adamic doctrine of Original Sin was deep in Judaism and Paul was just picking it up, and the answer is actually it isn't. Talk to conservative Jews, liberal Jews, second Temple Jews, there isn't a doctrine of Original Sin until 4th Ezra and 2 Baruch, which were written after the destruction of the temple in AD 70. Where the destruction of the temple has forced them to say *'we were aware of problems, but now we realize that it must be much worse than we'd ever imagined and maybe it all goes back to Adam after all.'*

And I think what you see in Paul is something very similar, that the death of Jesus has forced him to say *'the problem of the world must be much worse than we ever imagined. It has been solved by one man. Goodness, maybe that's actually what that story was about. It wasn't just a picture to get us going as it were.'*

In other words, just as the proto-Holocaust of the destruction of Jerusalem in AD70 caused the Jews newly to see a catastrophic human fall into sin in the Eden story, Paul had already come to such a view *de novo* for a much better reason – the tremendous cost to God of the Incarnation and Passion of Christ.

It is like the new emphasis on God's final judgement seen in the New Testament, and particularly in Jesus's own teaching – the fact of the Cross and the God-forsakenness of Jesus is a graphic demonstration of the necessary reality of judgement. The Church could not circumvent it without denying Christ. And Romans 5, as Wright points out, does a similar job for the Fall of mankind.

How, in detail, would Wright picture his primal couple? Perhaps he will write on it some day – perhaps someone can tell me he already has. But since his whole view of the New Testament is (notoriously) based on Old Testament covenant concepts, as penman suggest his view of Adam is likely to be similar. Throughout the Hebrew Scriptures, individuals are called from the mass of humanity to mediate God's covenant-making with his people. Noah is called from the descendants of Adam to re-boot humanity. Abram is called from Noah's line to initiate the salvation covenant. Similarly Moses is separated out from the captive Israel to bring release and blessing, David from the nation to found an eternal governing house and, at last, Messiah is promised, who will bring all things to fruition in a new covenant.

So the idea of Adam as a covenantal figure is completely consistent with the Old Testament, and is not just an *ad hoc* reaction to evolutionary ideas. Indeed, Reformed teachers have spoken of the first "covenant of works" with Adam for centuries. All that is new is the idea that Adam wasn't alone in the world when God called him – and that too may even be assumed by the Genesis text, whose roots in Mesopotamian literature also link the origins of "man" to the beginnings of religious society rather than the beginnings of matter.

Besides, Old Testament and ANE scholarship have shown that Paul's idea of Adam as a type of Christ is far more viable than the oft-suggested ideas of Adam being either an allegorical representation of "Everyman" or of "Israel" in their propensity to sin. Neither the OT nor other ANE texts have such a concept of allegory, as ANE specialist John H Walton informed me when I asked him directly.

But they do, Walton shows, portray *archetypes* – historical (or purportedly historical) figures whose experience mirrors our own. Such was Gilgamesh, whose failure to find a much desired immortality foreshadowed, rather than merely echoing, our own. Adam, too, is "first of a type" rather than "symbol of a type".

Adam's fall does not so much explain sin, as bring home its devastating effect on humanity and what Christ must undergo to remedy it. No other account does justice to that, and N T Wright has done us a service in showing how that must have been Paul's apostolic and Spirit-led conclusion too.

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Wright right about Ezra, or wrong about Esdras?

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A couple of months ago I embarked on reading (intermittently) through the Old Testament Apocrypha, most of which I've not read before, though it contains useful insights into the times between the testaments. Reading 2 Esdras in the *New English Bible*, I realised it was the same as the "4th Ezra" cited by Tom Wright in the quote I included in the above piece on Adam. There he says:

[In Judaism] there isn't a doctrine of Original Sin until 4th Ezra and 2 Baruch, which were written after the destruction of the temple in AD 70. Where the destruction of the temple has forced them to say *'we were aware of problems, but now we realize that it must be much worse than we'd ever imagined and maybe it all goes back to Adam after all.'*

In fact I didn't make the connection between the two until I looked up the "date and authorship" and remembered what Wright had said. But I'm not quite convinced by his suggestion that the author was making a bold new extrapolation from the story of the Fall, which had more or less coincidentally also been made by Paul in Romans a few years before in Romans 5. He, says Wright, was responding to the enormity of the Passion – they to the enormity of the destruction of Jerusalem.

I don't doubt the high relief into which either event throws human sin, but it seems to me that the idea was at least known, if not universal, and that we are just incomplete on our sources. For in the book, Ezra has various conversations with Uriel the archangel, who apocalyptically reveals hidden truths about God's judgement, and so on. Each section is introduced by Ezra's

prayer for enlightenment, and it is in one of these, rather than in the revelatory response, that the Fall is mentioned:

“You commanded the dust, and Adam appeared. His body was lifeless; but yours were the hands that had moulded it, and into it you breathed the breath of life. So you made him a living person. You led him into paradise, which you yourself had planted before the earth came into being. You gave him one commandment to obey he disobeyed it, and thereupon you made him subject to death, him and his descendants.”

The writer seems here to be recounting “what we already know from the Genesis account”, culminating in Adam as the author of death for all mankind through one act of disobedience. It’s also interesting how paradise is seen as a separate realm to the rest of earth, and Genesis 2 as describing a creation *before* that of Genesis 1 – one for the Young Earth Creationists to work on!

But Ezra’s prayer goes on:

“From him were born nations and tribes, people and families, too numerous to count. Each nation went its own way, sinning against you and scorning you; and you did not stop them ...”

He describes the Flood and the call of the Patriarchs just as conventional Christian teaching would understand them, and then the disobedience of Israel in terms taken directly from Deuteronomy 29:4 with its reference to lack of saving grace – linking it to Adam:

“But you did not take away their wicked heart and enable your law to bear fruit in them. For the first man, Adam, was burdened with a wicked heart; he sinned and was overcome, and not only he but all his descendants. So the weakness became inveterate. Although your law was in your people’s hearts, a rooted wickedness was there too; so that the good came to nothing, and what was bad persisted.”

That account would be a completely unremarkable summary of original sin in Christian terms, including an Augustinian description of its inherited nature – missing out only the concept of inherited guilt for Adam’s sin, which (though controversial even in Christianity) takes its root from Paul’s comparison in Romans 5 of the one act of Adam and the one act of Jesus. Yet 2 Esdras/4 Ezra is a Jewish work, not derived from Paul (I should note, for completeness, that the first two chapters are thought to be 3rd or 4th century Christian interpolation, but we are not dealing with those chapters).

The angel who replies alludes back to the Adam story, but once more simply to confirm and emphasise its truth – not, from the phraseology, to establish it as sensational new teaching:

“A grain of the evil seed was sown in the heart of Adam from the first; how much more godlessness has it produced already! How much more will it produce before the harvest!”

The writer, despite his less-than-Christian theology of atonement, has almost as much a sense of “total depravity” as Paul, or Calvin, as Ezra replies:

“But, my lord, my master,” I replied, “we are all of us sinners through and through. Can it be that, because of us, because of the sins of mankind, the harvest and reward of the [few] just are delayed?”

Later (ch7) Ezra, bewailing the wideness and finality of the coming judgement, even refers to Adam’s sin specifically as a “fall”:

“O Adam, what have you done? Your sin was not your fall alone; it was ours also, the fall of all your descendants.”

So was this doctrine of the Fall a new interpretation of Genesis prompted, independently, by the Christ’s Passion for Christians and by Jerusalem’s destruction for Jews? Or was it instead an understanding of what Genesis taught that had been known amongst Jews, despite the lack of surviving literary sources for it, for at least decades if not much longer? I’m easy either way – Wright’s picture of Paul grappling to such a conclusion from the death of Jesus is dramatic and compelling. On the other hand, if the importance of a historical Adam to the origin of sin predates Paul, then it’s more fundamental to both Jewish and Christian theology than is often acknowledged now.

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